

CLASSIFICATION OF COMPOUND SENTENCES IN WORLD LINGUISTICS

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The history of the study of syntax goes back to the ancient centuries. Under the syntax is understood the doctrine of the sentence and its parts. This theory arose from the expression of the linguistic traditions of antiquity. Syntax (from Greek syntax — unification, structure) is considered a level of the language system and consists of word forms. The question of syntax has been studied since antiquity, and syntactic issues are still relevant. Syntax is seen as a branch of grammar science. It is known that the science of grammar consists of two parts, namely the directions of morphology and syntax. The definition of syntax is approached in every possible way by English, Russian and Uzbek scientists. In particular, the Russian scientist V. V. Vinogradov believes that syntax is a science that studies the rules and methods of conjugation of a word and the composition of a sentence, and vocabulary, their structure, function, laws of development. "The scientist noted that a characteristic feature of syntax is that each object of its study functions as a structural element of a grammatical unit higher than it is: a word and its forms serve as a structural element of a word and a sentence, a vocabulary of various common statements, and in the framework of a sentence, in turn, a simple sentence serves as a structural element thus, syntax affirms that the object of learning is a sentence. Currently, V.Vinorgadov's theory and doctrine have found their place in the textbook of secondary schools, that is, in the education of schoolchildren, it is this scientist who relies on his thoughts. The syntax of the Uzbek language as a separate branch of linguistics was initially studied by Fitrat under the term "Nahv". H.Caiumius and C.Dolimov also wrote a two-part work, "grammar", and called the second part "nahv". [6] Gap theory has also been extensively studied by various researchers. Language performs its communicative function in a syntactic device — gap tool. All — phonetic, lexical, morphological phenomenon in the language serves this syntactic construction. However, among these, the involvement of Lexicon and morphology in the grammatical construction of language is unique. After all, in any syntactic phenomenon we see a word and a morphological indicator. Therefore, a lexical and morphological factor is relied upon in defining the syntactic essence. Due to the fact that the sentence is also

based on the free conjugation of the word, the law of the connection of the word, the vocabulary is also studied in the syntax. The study of vocabulary can not be considered as a component of the doctrine of the sentence, separated from it. The syntax examines not any conjugation of a word, but the linguistic nature of the free-speech conjugation, which is entered into a governor-tobelic relationship. A compound word (triangle, ertapishar, buy), a phraseological unit (which licks the fat of a snake, does not wind through its beak, is disillusioned), is left out of the study scope of syntax. Because they do not have a free connection. The term syntax is ambiguous, as is the term grammar itself: 1) the syntactic construction of a language; 2) a component of a grammar. Using the term in this second sense, we use the term syntactic construction for the expression of the first meaning.

In world linguistics, compound sentences are classified based on various criteria such as syntactic structure, semantic relationships between clauses, and discourse functions. Different linguists and theorists have proposed theories to explain the classification of compound sentences. Here are some key theories and approaches:

1. Syntactic Classification:

- Coordination: This type of compound sentence consists of two or more independent clauses joined by coordinating conjunctions like "and," "but," "or," etc.

- Subordination: In this type, one clause is dependent on the other, forming a complex sentence. Subordinating conjunctions like "because," "although," "when" are used to link the clauses.

2. Semantic Classification:

- Paratactic: Clauses in a paratactic compound sentence are equal in status and are usually connected by coordinating conjunctions. The relationship between the clauses is often one of coordination.

- Hypotactic: Clauses in a hypotactic compound sentence show a relationship where one clause is subordinate to the other. Subordinating conjunctions are used to indicate this relationship.

3. Functional Classification:

- Additive: Clauses in an additive compound sentence provide additional information or add new information to the preceding clause.

- Adversative: Clauses in an adversative compound sentence express contrast or opposition to the preceding clause.

- Causal: Clauses in a causal compound sentence show a cause-effect relationship between the clauses.

- Temporal: Clauses in a temporal compound sentence indicate a sequence of events or actions.

4. Discourse-based Classification:

- Continuative: Clauses in a continuative compound sentence continue the same line of thought or topic from the preceding clause.

- Disjunctive: Clauses in a disjunctive compound sentence present alternatives or choices.

- Conclusive: Clauses in a conclusive compound sentence provide a conclusion or result based on the preceding clause.

Prominent linguists like Noam Chomsky, Roman Jakobson, and Charles Fillmore have contributed to our understanding of compound sentences and their classification within linguistic theory. Their work has helped shape our knowledge of syntax, semantics, and discourse structures in compound sentences

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